

Schrodinger Equation in a Dilated Frame

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. and S.P.N. Messina, Nov. 4, 2019

There has been interest in the form of the Schrodinger equation in different noninertial frames for many decades, especially the rotating frame. Recently, transforming from one frame to another is described by using Lorentz boosts followed by a nonrelativistic limit (1). In this note, we consider the case of dilating objects which expand in such a way that the change in density is constant throughout the body. We then try to obtain a time-independent Schrodinger equation in the dilating frame. The results seem to be similar to the rotating case, although there the generator is $L_z = r \times p$ while for the dilating case, it is $r \cdot p$. It is possible that such a scenario of dilation may apply to heavy nuclei which have undergone a collision, are heated and are expanding slowly.

Dilations

Consider first the one dimensional case for which there are little slices with one boundary at x and the other at $x+dx$. There is also a velocity $v(x)$. The slices may lie between $-a \leq x \leq a$. After a time dt , both boundaries may shift to $a+da$ and $-a-da$ in such a way that each little slice has a new density, but one that is constant throughout the body. We will call this a dilation. Then, the increase in area of a slice is:

$$(v(x)dt + d/dx v dt - v(x)dt) = d/dx v dt = \text{constant} \quad \text{so} \quad v = C_1 x \quad \text{where } C_1 \text{ is a constant} \quad ((1))$$

For a dilation, one wants to ensure density remains constant throughout the body.

Next, consider a 3D spherical problem. In this case, there are spherical shells instead of slices. The increase in volume is:

$4(3.14)/3((r+dr+v(r)dt + d/dr v(r) dt)^3 - (r+v dt)^3)$ leading to an increase in shell volume to first order:

$$4(3.14) r^2 d/dr v(r) dt = dV \quad \text{Then: Change in density of a shell} = M/(V+dV) = (M/V) (1-dV/V)$$

Where $V=4(3.14)r^2dr$

For the change in density to be independent of r : $d/dr v(r) = \text{constant}$ or $v(r) = C_1 r$ ((2))

Thus, one has a type of constrained velocity in the r direction. For rotational motion, this constrained velocity is ωr . Thus, it seems that one could go into a 'dilated' frame moving with constrained velocity $v(r) = C_1 r$.

Lorentz Boosts for Constrained Motion

In (1), changes to different frames $v = v' + A(r)$ (where all three terms are vectors) is treated using a Lorentz boost, followed by a nonrelativistic expansion. The general result for the Hamiltonian in frame 2 (the rotating or dilating frame) is given by:

$$(1/2m) (-id_j - mA_j(r)) (-id_j - mA_j(r)) W(r) - .5m A_j(r)A_j(r) W(r) + V(r)W(r) = E W(r) \quad ((3))$$

Here $d_j = d/dr_j$ and there is a summation on $j=1,2,3$ (for x, y, z).

Equation ((3)) may be expanded so that one has a term $(-1/2m)d_j d_j$ and term involving the generator of noninertial frame. The term $(1/2) mA_j A_j$ cancels with $-.5m A_j(r)A_j(r)$.

An alternative approach for dealing with noninertial frames is given in (2), where the Hamiltonian in the accelerated frame is given by:

$$H' = i d/dt S S^+ + S H S^+ \quad \text{and } S = \exp(iK) \text{ so } d/dt e^{iK} e^{-iK} = id/dtK + ii/2 [K, d/dtK] \dots \quad ((3a))$$

K is given in (1) as a Galilean boost $tA \cdot p - mA \cdot x$ where $x = x' + A$. This is then in turn given by:

$t \cdot 5mA \cdot A - mA \cdot x$ so only the first term remains in ((3a)).

For the case of $A = \omega \times r$ (i.e. a rotation about the z axis), one may consider a simple harmonic oscillator in 2D with a ground state solution of $\exp(-.5\sqrt{k/m}x^2)\exp(-.5\sqrt{k/m}y^2)$. In such case, L_z acting on this wavefunction is zero, so it is a solution of both the lab frame equation and the rotating frame equation, with E being the same for both.

For the case of dilations, $A(r)$ vector = $(r_j/r) C_1 r$ or $C_1 r_j$ ((4))

Then, ((3)) yields:

$$(1/2m) (-d_j d_j - 2i C_1 m r_j d_j + m i^3 C_1^3) W(r) + V(r)W(r) = E W(r) \quad ((5))$$

Thus, the generator of dilations seems to be $-2i r_j d_j$ or $2 r_j p_j$ in analogy to $-i e_{ijk} r_j d_k = L_z$ for rotations.

One may see that there are imaginary terms in ((5)) indicating that there is one directional velocity flow.

One may try a possible solution to ((5)) of the form $\exp(iC_1 m r^2/2)$. In such a case:

$$-d_j d_j (\exp(iC_1 m r^2/2) W) = (-3imC_1 W - d_j d_j W + 2imC_1 r_j d_j W + mmC_1 C_1 r r W) \exp(iC_1 m r^2/2)$$

And

$$-2iC_1 m r_j d_j ((\exp(iC_1 m r^2/2) W)) = (2C_1 C_1 m r r W - 2iC_1 m r_j d_j W) \exp(iC_1 m r^2/2)$$

Thus, it seems that $W(r) \exp(iC_1 m r^2/2)$ is a solution of the Schrodinger equation in a dilating frame.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have attempted to examine the case of a dilating system and have made some comparisons with a rotating frame. It is possible that a dilating system

may apply to highly heated large nuclei which have undergone strong collisions. In some cases, these are treated as a Fermi gas. Perhaps the equation in the dilated frame might add some extra restrictions to the state of the expanding nuclei.

References

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